

Damage And Fracture In Notched Woven Fabric Composites Under Cyclic Loading

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Abstract

Fatigue of notched woven GFRP and CFRP laminates under tension-tension fatigue loading was investigated. It was shown that the damage morphology which developed under cyclic loading of a four-layer quasi-isotropic glass laminate, based on eight harness satin weave (8HS) reinforcement, was similar to that observed previously under quasi-static loading. Under fatigue loading, however, the extent (length) of the damage zone prior to final fracture was greater than seen under quasi-static loading and the extent increased with reducing fatigue stress in the fatigue cycle. This trend was modelled reasonably well by the fracture mechanics element of a model developed to predict the strength under quasi-static loading. CFRP laminates – which were also four-layer quasi-isotropic lay-ups, but based on plain weave (PW) or five harness satin (5HS) reinforcement – showed a slight improvement in residual strength with increasing fatigue cycles. The improvement was not sufficiently high, however, to suggest that the effect of the notch had been eliminated completely.

Keywords: Composites, Woven, Notched, Fatigue.

1 Introduction

In recent work [1, 2], we have developed a physically-based model for the notched strength of woven fabric composites subjected to quasi-static loading. The model is based on the experimental observation of self-similar damage growth from the tip of the stress raiser; the damage zone involves matrix cracking and fibre tow fracture and can be approximated as a through-thickness crack. The approach has been found to be applicable to a range of woven fabric-based materials, weave types and notch geometries. The aim of the present paper is to examine the behaviour of notched laminates under tension-tension fatigue loading, in particular to examine whether the physically-based model assists in interpreting fatigue data. Previous work on fatigue of notched woven CFRP laminates by Curtis and Moore [3] showed an increase in residual strength with fatigue cycling, suggesting that there is a notch blunting mechanism in fatigue. In the present investigation, similar work to that of Curtis and Moore was carried out on GFRP as well as CFRP laminates.

The structure of the paper is as follows: in the next section the material and experimental methods are detailed, in the following section the experimental results are shown and discussed and in the last section the concluding remarks are presented.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material Preparation

There were three different woven composite laminates investigated in this study; a quasi-isotropic glass fibre reinforced laminate (8Q4), a quasi-isotropic carbon fibre reinforced laminate (5Q4) and a plain weave carbon fibre reinforced laminate (PQ4). The GFRP laminate was a four layer quasi-isotropic E-glass eight harness satin weave reinforced laminate with an epoxy matrix. The CFRP laminates were four layer quasi-isotropic five harness satin and plain weave carbon fibre reinforced laminates with an epoxy matrix. The difference between the three laminates is the reinforcement, where one is glass (eight harness satin) and the others are carbon (five harness satin and plain weave).

2.1.1 Preparation of the GFRP Laminate

The GFRP laminate was a quasi-isotropic (0/90/+45/-45/-45/+45/90/0) woven fabric reinforced composite laminate. The fibre reinforcement was a Fothergill Engineered Fabrics Ltd. Y0227 E-glass continuous eight harness satin (8HS) weave fabric (British Standard 3396 S2/22) with a Methacrylate

Chromic Chloride finish (Code 205). The resin matrix was a Shell Epikote 828 (Bisphenol-A) epoxy resin system with a Shell epicure nadic methyl anhydride (NMA) curing agent and Ancamine K61B accelerator. Laminates were manufactured using an in-house wet lay-up process; a detailed account of this process can be found in [1]. The manufacturing method produces generally very good quality laminates with some minor defects, such as voids and resin poor regions. Test coupons, 25 mm by 250 mm, were prepared for fatigue and quasi-static investigations. The coupons were post-cured at 150°C for 3 hours between glass plates to prevent warping. A circular centre hole of 5 mm diameter was introduced into the coupons, using low helix, high-speed steel drill bits normally for use with thermosetting polymers.

2.1.2 Preparation of the CFRP Laminates

Both the plain weave (PW) and five harness satin (5HS) weave carbon fibre laminates were manufactured from Primco pre-pregs, which were made using the Toray T300 high strength carbon fibre. The matrix was a Vantico MY750 epoxy resin system. The carbon fibre reinforced laminates were fabricated by St. Bernards Composites Ltd as one metre square panels. The lay-up sequence for both the PW and 5HS CFRP laminates was (0/90/+45/-45/-45/+45/90/0), a quasi-isotropic lay-up.

After manufacture the CFRP panels were ultrasonically C-scanned at DERA (QinetiQ) to investigate the presence and extent of defects. The C-scan results showed that there were some areas on the panels that contained some porosity, but even in the worst cases the extent of porosity was below 3%. These regions were avoided when cutting coupons from the panels. Coupons of 25 mm by 250 mm were prepared from the panels. A circular centre hole of 5 mm diameter was introduced into the coupons, using low helix, high-speed steel drill bit normally for use with thermosetting polymers.

2.2 Mechanical Testing

The coupons had aluminium end tabs of 25 x 50 mm bonded to both sides of the coupon ends using 3M Scotch-Weld DP 490 structural adhesive, producing a tabbed coupon with a 150 mm gauge length. All the specimens were fatigue tested in an Instron 1341 machine with servo-hydraulic grips, at room temperature. The tests were carried out in load control at a frequency of 10 Hz and sinusoidal waveform. The fatigue loading was tension-tension, with a fatigue stress ratio of $R=0.1$. Load, extension and cycle data were recorded using a PC data-logging package from MTS. The fatigue tests were carried out on notched 5 mm diameter circular centre holed coupons to evaluate the residual strength after 5000, 50,000 and 500,000 cycles.

The quasi-static tensile testing was carried out using an Instron 5500R at a constant crosshead displacement of 0.5 mm/min. The ASTM standard D 3039 was followed wherever possible in determining the strength of the notched coupons after fatigue loading.

2.3 Damage Observations

Observations of damage accumulation were made by *in-situ* plan view observations using conventional light photography and video recording. The term plan view damage is used to describe the damage formed, which is visible perpendicular to the plane of the laminate. Utilising the transparent nature of the GFRP laminate, damage development at the hole edge could be monitored by illuminating the samples from behind. This gave a good indication of the extent of damage, but little information about the nature of the damage. To study the extent of fibre tow failure it was necessary to study the damage layer-by-layer. This involved fatigue loading a notched coupon until a damage zone formed. Then the coupon regions near the hole, which contained the damage, were sectioned and the matrix was burnt off to expose the reinforcement. The damaged reinforcements were gold coated and viewed in a variable pressure Hitachi environmental S300N scanning electron microscope (SEM) using secondary electron imaging mode. Each layer of the reinforcement was examined separately, using the depth of focus of the SEM to determine the extent of fibre damage.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 GFRP Fatigue Results

For the glass fibre reinforced coupons, three different maximum peak stresses were used for the fatigue testing. At each peak stress, the minimum stress was modified to keep the stress ratio at 0.1. The peak stresses were 85%, 75% and 60% of the average notched strength for a 5 mm circular hole (average notched strength is ~150 MPa [1]) and the loadings are designated regimes A, B and C, respectively.

The reason for the different peak loads for the GFRP coupons is that when the first specimen was fatigue tested at 85% it failed after just 6028 cycles. This suggested, perhaps not surprisingly, that the GFRP samples at this stress level were experiencing a fatigue failure rather than the notch blunting and increase in residual strength reported in the literature for CFRP. To check this hypothesis three unnotched coupons were fatigue tested to failure with a peak fatigue stress equal to 55% of the unnotched strength (average unnotched strength is ~290 MPa [1]). A peak stress of 55% of the unnotched strength gives a maximum stress of ~160 MPa in the fatigue cycle. This is equivalent to the stress carried by the effective cross-section of the notched coupon with a peak fatigue stress of 85% of the average notched strength and a 5 mm circular centre hole. This means that carrying out the fatigue tests on the unnotched coupon at a maximum peak stress of 55% of the unnotched strength, can be viewed as equivalent to carrying out fatigue tests of notched coupons at 85% of their strength, but without the effect of the notch. The three unnotched coupons tested at a peak fatigue stress of 55% of the unnotched strength failed at around 100,000 cycles. This shows that the GFRP had definite S-N curve behaviour and the notched samples would have failed due to fatigue on the basis of the net-section stress; this failure was simply exacerbated by the presence of a notch, so that the coupon failed after a lower number of cycles.

The results of the fatigue tests that were carried out on the GFRP coupons are presented in Table 1. Whilst the numbers of cycles to failure show some scatter, there is reasonable consistency for the number of cycles to failure under each loading regime. All the notched specimens failed through the notch, after showing broadly similar damage morphology to that observed for the GFRP coupons under quasi-static tensile testing [1].

Table 1. Fatigue Test Results for the GFRP Laminate

Regime	Specimen	Notch Size - <i>d</i> (mm)	Cycles to Failure - <i>N</i>
A	8HS-I1	5	6028
B	8HS-I2	5	40,484
	8HS-I4	5	17,172
	8HS-I5	5	15,091
	8HS-I7	5	11,002
	8HS-I9	5	10,304
C	8HS-I3	5	319,154
	8HS-I6	5	154,512
	8HS-H4	5	212,262
	8HS-H5	5	195,872
Unnotched	8HS-G5	0	80,592
	8HS-G3	0	109,692
	8HS-G4	0	104,104

3.2 GFRP Damage Observations

3.2.1 *In-situ* Plan View Damage Observations

Coupon 8HS-I8 was fatigued at a peak fatigue stress which was 60% of the average notched strength (Regime C) and the test was terminated after 200,000 cycles (which is about 90% of the average number of cycles to failure for these conditions). During the fatigue testing of this coupon, plan view

photographs were taken at regular intervals to show the development of the damage up to 200,000 cycles and figures 1 to 6 provide a sequence of *in-situ* plan view photographs showing the damage development.

Fig. 1 *In-situ* photograph showing coupon 8HS-I8 at 1500 cycles.

Fig. 2 *In-situ* photograph showing coupon 8HS-I8 at 20,000 cycles.

Fig. 3 *In-situ* photograph showing coupon 8HS-I8 at 110,000 cycles.

Fig. 4 *In-situ* photograph showing coupon 8HS-I8 at 135,000 cycles.

Fig. 5 *In-situ* photograph showing coupon 8HS-I8 at 150,000 cycles.

Fig. 6 *In-situ* photograph showing coupon 8HS-I8 at 200,000 cycles.

The sequence of damage development shown in these figures is very similar to that seen for quasi-static tensile testing [1]. Damage begins with matrix cracking near the notch, which gradually increases in density with increasing number of cycles. The matrix cracking spreads on both sides of the hole whilst being more intense near the hole, and there is evidence of cracking at $\pm 45^\circ$ as well as at 90° . After about 100,000 fatigue cycles (figure 3), a particularly intense region of damage begins to form at both notch edges. This intense region of damage consisted of a very high density of matrix cracking, together with delamination and some 0° fibre failure (see next section). As with the quasi-static tensile tests, this “damage zone” initially propagates stably so that by 200,000 cycles (figure 6), its length on each side of the hole is about a quarter of the coupon width. Eventually the damage zone reaches a critical length and then propagates catastrophically to failure (this was observed in other coupons). The main difference between the quasi-static and cyclic damage zone development is that the width and length of the damage zone formed under fatigue are both larger than for quasi-static tensile testing [1].

From video records of the fatigue tests, the “critical damage zone” dimensions were measured using a simple rectangle representation (see figure 7), which was also used for the quasi-static “critical damage zones” [1]. The results of the measurements of the dimensions of the critical damage zone are shown in Table 2, together with the average critical damage zone measurements obtained for quasi-static loading of 5 mm circular centre holed coupons [1]. The table shows that the length of the critical damage zones under fatigue were longer than those seen under quasi-static loading. In addition, a lower peak fatigue stress produced a longer damage zone.

Fig. 7 Schematic model of damage zone.

Table 2. Dimensions of the Critical Damage Zone Developed Under Fatigue Loading.

Regime	Coupon	W (mm)	d (mm)	w _l (mm)	w _r (mm)	l _l (mm)	l _r (mm)	Peak Stress (MPa)
B (Fatigue)	8HS-I4	25.1	5	3.4	3.7	5.0	5.4	113
	8HS-I5	25.1	5	3.1	3.2	4.4	5.1	113
	8HS-I7	25.1	5	3.8	3.3	4.9	5.2	113
	8HS-I9	25.1	5	3.4	3.5	4.2	5.3	113
C (Fatigue)	8HS-I6	25.2	5	3.7	4.0	6.3	6.6	90.4
	8HS-H4	25.2	5	4.1	3.9	6.9	6.2	90.4
	8HS-H5	25.1	5	3.3	4.1	6.2	6.9	90.4
Quasi-Static	Average	25.0	5	1.6	1.7	1.9	2.0	147

3.2.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy

After the fatigue loading of coupon 8HS-I8 was completed (at 200000 cycles), the regions of the coupon near the notch that contained the damage zone were sectioned and the matrix was burnt off to expose the reinforcement. The exposed reinforcement was then examined using a SEM, so that the damage close to the hole could be studied in more detail. The fabric layers were separated giving four layers; the first layer was (0/90) orientated, the second (+45/-45), the third (-45/+45) and the final layer was (90/0) orientated. Figures 8 to 10 show the secondary electron micrographs of the fatigue damage adjacent to the 5 mm circular centre hole for each layer. Figure 8 is a micrograph of the damage on the right hand side of the hole of the first layer, which was (0/90) orientated and shows damage to, and failure of, the 0° fibres up to nine tows away from the hole edge. The damage and tow fractures observed after fatigue loading were not as co-planar as those seen under quasi-static loading [1], and although there is very clear evidence of 0° fibre failure, it is not always clear that entire tows have completely failed. The damage observed on the right hand side of the hole was similar to that seen on the left hand side of the hole. Figure 9 shows the third layer, the ± 45 orientated layer, which shows signs of damage and even some fibre failure that was not observed under quasi-static loading. The region of damage in the ± 45 layer is not directly adjacent to the hole edge but lies about 1 mm away. The damage observed in the third layer was similar to that seen for the second layer, which was also a ± 45 layer. Figure 10 shows the damage on the right hand side of the hole for the fourth layer, which was (0/90) orientated, and again there is evidence of damage and failure of the 0° fibres this time up to ten tows away from the hole edge. As in the first (0/90) layer, the damage observed on the right hand side of the hole was similar to that on the left hand side of the hole and the damage to the tows after fatigue loading was not as co-planar as it was under quasi-static loading. Again, there is clear evidence of 0° fibre tow failure, but it is not clear whether all the fibres up to ten tows from the hole edge have failed.

Fig. 8 Secondary electron micrograph showing fatigue damage on the right side of a 5 mm circular centre hole in the first (0/90) layer.

Fig. 9 Secondary electron micrograph showing fatigue damage adjacent to both sides of a 5 mm circular centre hole in the third (+45/-45) layer.

Fig. 10 Secondary electron micrograph showing fatigue damage on the right side of a 5 mm circular centre hole in the fourth (0/90) layer.

3.3 Quantitative Investigation of the GFRP Fatigue Data

The increase in the critical damage zone size with reducing peak stress is consistent with fracture mechanics. The CDG model [1] for predicting quasi-static strength contains a fracture mechanics component and it is therefore possible to use the CDG model to estimate the critical damage zone length prior to catastrophic crack growth in the fatigue tests.

Figure 11 is a plot of the data from Table 2., together with the relevant fracture mechanics expression (Equation 1), which is used in the CDG model.

$$K_c = \sigma_1 \sqrt{\pi c F_0 Y_2} \quad (1)$$

In equation 1, K_c is the critical stress intensity factor, σ_1 is the remote applied stress, c is the length of the crack and F_0 is a correction factor for cracks growing from a circular hole in an isotropic plate.

From [1], the average experimentally measured critical damage zone length for the GFRP laminate with a 5 mm circular centre hole was approximately 2 mm when tested under quasi-static loading. This is also the critical damage zone length predicted by the CDG model. In figure 11 the predicted notched strength, σ_N , for a 5 mm circular centre hole in the GFRP laminate is shown as a function of the critical damage zone length according to the fracture mechanics relation used in the CDG model. Obviously, very small damage zone lengths correspond to high notched strengths and the notched strength falls with increasing damage zone length. The same graph shows the maximum peak stress for the specimens fatigued in Regimes B and C (see Table 1). The specimens failed at these peak

fatigue stress values and measurements were made of the critical damage zone lengths prior to failure. In both cases there is reasonable agreement between the predicted damage zone length according to the fracture mechanics relation and the measured values, although the measured damage zone lengths are about 75% of the predicted values. Figure 11 shows clearly that the damage zone length is larger for fatigue loading than quasi-static loading and that the damage zone length is larger at lower fatigue stress levels.

Fig. 11 Graph of stress against damage zone length, where σ_N is the predicted notched strength for a 5 mm circular centre hole, $0.75 \sigma_N$ and $0.6 \sigma_N$ are 75% and 60% of the average notched strength and the peak stress for Regimes B and C respectively.

3.4 CFRP Fatigue Results

Unlike the GFRP laminates, all except one of the CFRP specimens survived the fatigue loading at 85% of the average quasi-static notched strength of the laminate. The one exception was coupon PQ4-H3, which failed after 388,227 cycles, but as it was the only carbon specimen to fail under fatigue it is considered an anomaly that failed prematurely due to possible defects such as voids or perhaps a load spike. After the coupons had been fatigue cycled for 5000, 50,000 or 500,000 cycles, they were then tested to failure under quasi-static tensile loading and the results are presented in Table 3. Also shown in Table 3 are the average quasi-static notched strength values for coupons with no prior fatigue loading (the average and the standard deviation are shown [4]). In the residual strength tests for coupons with prior fatigue cycling, all the specimens failed through the notch.

As shown in Table 3., the average notched strength for a 5 mm circular centre hole for the PQ4 laminate was 239 MPa and for the 5Q4 laminate it was 202 MPa. These results show that there was little difference between the quasi-static strength results for the coupons that had been fatigue loaded for 5000, 50,000 and 500,000 cycles.

The results of the 5Q4 laminate show an improvement in residual strength of about 10% after fatigue loading. So the enhanced strength value after fatigue cycling is not, however, comparable to the

average *unnotched* strength of the 5Q4 laminate (375 ± 22 MPa [4]), when the reduction in area due to the hole is taken into consideration. Hence, although there was an improvement in the notched strength of the 5Q4 laminate after fatigue loading (consistent with previous work [3]), it cannot be said that the increase in strength was sufficiently high for the effect of the notch to have been completely eliminated. This suggests that the damage formed during fatigue of the 5Q4 laminate reduced the effect of the notch. The damage formed would have been longitudinal splitting adjacent to the hole, which was not sufficient to remove completely the effect of the notch but was long enough to reduce its effect partially.

Table 3. Quasi-static Tensile Test Results for the CFRP Laminates

Laminate	Quasi-static Average Strength (without fatigue Loading) (MPa)	Fatigue Cycles	Specimen	Notch Size (d) (mm)	Strength (MPa)	Avg. Str. (MPa)	Std Dev (MPa)
PQ4	239 ± 6.8	500000	PQ4-H1	5	235	224	12.2
			PQ4-H2	5	226		
			PQ4-E4	5	211		
		50000	PQ4-H4	5	226	219	23.5
			PQ4-H5	5	238		
			PQ4-E3	5	193		
		5000	PQ4-H7	5	224	225	5.6
			PQ4-H8	5	221		
			PQ4-E2	5	232		
5Q4	202 ± 4.7	500000	5Q4-G1	5	226	224	2.2
			5Q4-G2	5	226		
			5Q4-G3	5	222		
		50000	5Q4-G4	5	216	215	2.5
			5Q4-G5	5	212		
			5Q4-G6	5	215		
		5000	5Q4-G7	5	215	218	3.2
			5Q4-G8	5	219		
			5Q4-G9	5	221		

On the other hand, in the results for the PQ4 laminate, there is a much greater scatter in the results, but overall there was no improvement in the residual strength after fatigue loading, compared to the average quasi-static notched strength (390 ± 11 MPa [4]). It is not clear why the notched strength of the PQ4 laminate showed no improvement after fatigue loading, and further work (involving damage studies) would be required to investigate this.

5 Concluding Remarks

The results showed that the quasi-isotropic GFRP laminate was fatigue sensitive; there was a marked S-N curve as all the notched coupons tested failed through the notch under fatigue loading. It was found that for the GFRP laminate, the damage zone that formed during fatigue was similar to that seen under quasi-static tensile loading. Furthermore, the lengths of the critical damage zones were larger for fatigue loading than for quasi-static loading, due to the lower applied stress and the critical damage zone length was found to be longer at lower fatigue stress levels. It has also been shown that there is extensive evidence of 0° fibre failure, and in some cases tow failure, in the damage zone region. However, unlike the results for quasi-static tensile testing, there is also evidence of damage to fibres in the ± 45 layers. The results for critical damage zone length were consistent with the predictions of the CDG model.

The CFRP laminates showed little difference in residual strength values after fatigue cycling and hence can be said to be fatigue insensitive. The PQ4 laminate showed no significant improvement in

the residual strength after fatigue loading (in fact a small reduction was noted), whilst the 5Q4 laminate showed about a 10% improvement in strength after fatigue loading, irrespective of the number of fatigue cycles. The strength improvement in the 5Q4 laminate was not, however, comparable to the average un-notched strength showing that the effect of the notch has been reduced, but not eliminated.

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